

The Revelation: The earliest known use of ‘ajamī as a label

Our blog has the acronym A-LABEL: we deal a lot with the **African languages between the lines**. But why “label”? This is because the interlinear glosses written in African languages of West Africa often have a descriptive metalinguistic marker, asserting the presence of an Ajami segment. This marker is typically a graphic variation of the word ‘*ajamī* (عجمي – the form written on our logo) or ‘*ajam*. Another way of the metalinguistic labelling of the Ajami glosses found in the manuscripts is the Arabic phrase *fī kalāmīnā* ‘in our language’ (في كلامنا) and its variations (for the use of ‘*ajamī* and *fī kalāmīnā* in Soninke and other Mande manuscripts see Ogorodnikova 2017: 122-125).[\[1\]](#)

The earliest Soninke glosses marked with the word ‘*ajamī* are found in the manuscripts written around the early nineteenth century (Darya Ogorodnikova is exploring this question in her PhD thesis expected to see the light of day this summer).

In Hausa Ajami writing, various stylised forms of ‘*ajam(ī)* were frequently used (Dobronravin 2013: 91) and until last week we could date it to the first half of the nineteenth century, as in the manuscript below, where the word ‘*ajam* (encircled) is written in unconnected letters ‘*ayn*, *jīm* and *mīm*:

Shurūt al-‘ilm ‘The prerequisites of knowledge’. Kano, MS.Murtala. Before (?) mid-19th century.

A week ago, Nikolay Dobronravin discovered Hausa Ajami in a [dated manuscript of Maqāmāt al-Harīrī](#) possibly copied in 1166H/1752CE (or 1177H/1763CE, depending on interpretation of the numbers in the colophon).[\[2\]](#) If it is indeed mid-eighteenth century, this would make it the earliest dated Hausa glosses and also the earliest dated label ‘*ajamī* in the Hausa texts. You can see two tokens of ‘*ajam* at the bottom of the page:

Maqāmāt al-Harīrī, BNF/Gallica. Colophon: 1752 or 1763.

[ark:/12148/btv1b53151891k](https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:hbz:5:1-63862-p0101-9)

Moving further east, the manuscripts with Old Kanembu glosses are generally believed to lack the ‘*ajamī*’ label. I myself have previously stated as much (see Dobronravin 2013: 91, with a reference to Bondarev). I was wrong.

This conviction of mine was demolished a year ago while I re-investigated the famous dated Borno Qur’an, 1080H/1669CE (Bivar 1960, Bondarev 2006a, 2014). Previously, I had never noticed any instances of the word ‘*ajamī*’. Overlooking a word or a whole sentence in this and many other manuscripts is not so shocking – an [average page](#) of this 300-folio Qur’an requires hours and days to make sense of all connections between the main text and surrounding commentaries. In any case, while looking for an Old Kanembu word in *Sūrat al-Ahqāf* (Q.46), I stumbled upon this:

Qur’an. CSMC, Hamburg, MS.3ImI. Colophon: 1669.

Circled in yellow is our ‘*ajamī*’ (or ‘*ajam*’) in a stylised writing, with the “tail” of the letter *mīm* happily wagging left rather than submissively hanging down (as in common styles of writing). And this single occurrence of ‘*ajamī*’ makes it the oldest known case of labelling non-Arabic writing. I am convinced that it was written before 1669 since we know that the Old Kanembu glosses were added to the main Qur’an text first, while the voluminous Arabic commentary of al-Qurṭubī, which wraps around the main text, was done afterwards, in 1080/1669 (see Bondarev 2017: 119-122, 2019).

When I first noticed this ‘*ajam(ī)*’ I did not understand the meaning of the marked word, *krtsāk*, and I did not make a connection between this Old Kanembu word and the Qur’anic phrase *tanzīl al-kitābi* ‘the revelation of the Book (the Qur’an)’. I even fell in the fallacy of chance resemblance, trying to see in the word *krtsāk* the Ancient Greek *χάρτης* (*khártēs*) ‘papyrus scroll; book’. The Greek *khártēs* did actually make its way into Arabic and became *qirtās* to designate papyrus, parchment or paper (Gacek 2001: 114, Gacek 2009). Given the antiquity of Islam in Kanem-Borno (see a succinct overview in Bondarev 2006b), it would not be implausible that the term for ‘writing surface’ was borrowed from Arabic sometime in the early centuries of Islam. Even more so, it would make sense to look more closely at the Old Kanembu *krtsāk* because in the neighbouring Hausa language the word for paper is *takārdā* and it is indeed related to the Greek *khártēs*: it was borrowed from Berber (*t(a)*-being the feminine prefix in Berber) which in turn was borrowed from Latin *charta* (Kossmann 2005:77), the loanword from Ancient Greek *khártēs*.

Well, a closer look revealed to me the revelation. Quite literally. Because Old Kanembu *krtsāk* is not a translation of the Qur’anic *al-kitābi* (of the Book) but of the deverbal noun

tanzīl ‘the revelation’. This Arabic noun derives from stem II verb *nazzala* ‘send down; reveal’. A comparison of the same verse of the Qur’an (Q.46:2) in the other manuscripts dismantled the faintest traces of my χάρτης fantasy. For example, the manuscript MS.Tahir.Kano clearly tells us that <*alqurānka jrksākṭī allah kan kaṭīkō*> ‘the **revelation** of the Qur’an is from God’. The item marked in bold is the same deverbal noun as *krtsāk* in the dated Qur’an MS.3ImI. Both nouns share the same verb root *sāk* ‘descend’. So it turned out that to translate the Qur’anic notion of ‘sending down, revealing’, Old Kanembu uses an applicative form of the verb *sāk* which is *irgsāk* ‘to send down, bring down’. This form is then nominalised either with a prefix *k-* as in *k-rtsākh* or with a prefix *nz-* (written as <j>) as in *j-rksāk*. The range of graphemic variation of this deverbal noun is great in Old Kanembu manuscripts (the factors being both orthographic and morphological). But whatever the variation, we have the winner for the earliest non-Arabic word in West Africa marked with the label ‘*ajamī*’ and this word is Old Kanembu: *krtsāk* ‘revelation’.

There is one unsettling question: why only this instance of the word is marked with ‘*ajamī*’? Why no other verses but for Q.46:2 have it? I have checked all occurrences of Qur’anic *tanzīl* in the dated MS.3ImI. Thus, in 3ImI/Q.26:192 it is *krtsak*, in 3ImI/39:1 *ktsak*, in 3ImI/ Q.41:1 *kitsāk* and in 3ImI/ Q.69:43 *kktsak*. But none is marked as ‘*ajamī*’. I also looked up in the other places of MS.3ImI where *tanzīl* is mentioned – nothing: no *krtsākh* no ‘*ajamī*’.^[3]

And while diving again into my manuscript data in search of words for ‘descend’, I still could not find any other occurrence of ‘*ajamī*’ in the other manuscripts. It might well be that ‘*ajamī*’ in MS.3ImI Q.46:2 is a unique instance of this term – an exception confirming the rule and validating my earlier assumption about the lack of ‘*ajamī*’ in Old Kanembu manuscripts.

As for the words ‘paper’ and ‘book’ in Old Kanembu, I’ll leave it for another post.

[1] The paper of the manuscript looks almost a century younger! Manuscripts were often copied with the previous copyists’ colophons and we need to examine the paper first in such suspicious cases. Many thanks to Darya Ogorodnikova for having raised this question.

[2] Our Ajami Lab team is preparing a post on various types of such “labels” across West African manuscripts.

[3] These verses are as follows: MS.3ImI/Q.20:4, 32:2, 36:5, 40:1, 41:42, 45:2, and 56:80.

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